

Beyond the Classroom: Exploring the Role of Hobbies in Mitigating Academic Burnout for BS Computer Science Students at Isabela State University-Echague Campus

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RESEARCH ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Received: March 23, 2023 Reviewed: May 21, 2024 Accepted: June 01, 2024 Published: June 29, 2024</p> <p> Copyright © 2025 by the Author(s). This open-access article is distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.</p>	<p>This research aimed to determine whether hobbies help students in pursuing a bachelor's degree in Computer Science to minimize academic burnout. For students who experience physical, mental, and emotional stress along with insufficient sleep and free time, academic burnout can be a significant problem. These factors can lead to a loss of motivation and focus, which can have detrimental effects on both academic performance and overall well-being. To prevent such negative outcomes, students must prioritize self-care and adopt effective stress management strategies. The study involved 125 respondents who completed an online survey. The study measured specific burnout symptoms such as emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment. It explored hobbies including enrichment, sports, creative, social, collecting, and outdoor activities. Likert scales were used to measure academic burnout symptoms, experiences with hobbies, and the association between the two. The study's findings would contribute to the current literature on the effectiveness of hobbies in reducing academic burnout. It would also shed light on the benefits of engaging in hobbies and provide insight into how they can potentially eliminate academic burnout. Furthermore, the results address the gap in knowledge regarding the relationship between hobbies and academic burnout among Bachelor of Science in Computer Science students. Overall, the study provides valuable information that can be used</p>

to develop effective interventions to manage academic burnout among students. Thus, the researchers recommended that students should pick hobbies that can help students avoid academic burnout, manage it, and recover from it.

Keywords: *academic, burnout, Computer Science, hobbies, stress*

Introduction

Burnout is a condition of continuous stress and overwork-related physical, mental, and emotional fatigue (EduValsania et.al., 2022). Depersonalization, cynicism, and a diminished sense of personal accomplishment are their defining characteristics (Tabowei & Idahor,2022). People can experience burnout in a variety of contexts, including employment, school, caregiving, and interpersonal interactions (Nguyen-Phuoc et al.,2022). Chronic fatigue, a feeling of being overburdened or exhausted, a loss of desire or interest in activities, trouble concentrating, feelings of irritation, and decreased performance at work or school are some common signs of burnout (Prentice et.al., 2022). Physical signs of burnout might include headaches, gastrointestinal problems, and an increased risk of illness (Hu, 2023). High job demands, inadequate levels of support and autonomy, competing pressures, and a lack of control over one's work or life are just a few of the elements that can lead to burnout (Chen & Wu, 2022). It may also be brought on by long-term stress, sleep deprivation, inadequate nutrition, and insufficient exercise. Early burnout intervention is important for preventing it from becoming chronic (Renaldo, 2022). This could entail reaching out to friends, family, or mental health professionals for support, as well as altering your routines at home and work by prioritizing your well-being, practicing self-care, and setting boundaries (Sommovigo et al., 2022).

Students who are constantly stressed out and exhausted by their academic studies are said to be suffering from academic burnout, a particular sort of burnout (Basri et al., 2022). It is characterized by experiences of both physical and emotional tiredness, a diminished sense of personal success, and depersonalization in relation to academic labor (El Mouedden, 2022). Many variables, such as high academic demands, lack of social support, and lack of control over one's academic burden, can lead to academic burnout (Francisco et al., 2022). Lack of desire or interest in academic work, trouble focusing or remembering material, and sensations of dissatisfaction or inadequacy are some additional causes that can lead to academic burnout (Edu Valsania et al., 2022). Chronic fatigue, trouble focusing, feelings of apathy or disengagement, a loss of motivation or interest in academic work, lower academic performance, and an increased risk of illness are some of the signs of academic burnout (Springer, 2022). Managing stress and lowering demands on students are key to addressing academic burnout. This could entail getting help from academic advisors or mental health specialists, as well as coming up with plans for how to prioritize self-care and manage your workload in the classroom (Basri et al., 2022). In order to maintain balance and well-being, other strategies might include improving study habits, using relaxation techniques, and taking part in activities outside of the classroom (Bartlett et al., 2021).

In addition, a growing concern among students, especially those pursuing higher education, is academic burnout (Budge et al., 2020; Pascoe et al., 2020; Baik & Brooker, 2019; Lee et al., 2021; Budge et al., 2020; Pascoe et al., 2020; Lee et al., 2021) The

stress and pressure of academic demands combined with social and personal pressures can result in burnout, and a state of physical, emotional, and mental exhaustion (Salgado & Au-Yong, 2021). While numerous strategies have been suggested to deal with student burnout, little study has looked at the possible contribution of hobbies to lowering academic burnout (Kassam et al., 2021; Schilling & Randolph, 2021; Gaston-Hawkins et al., 2020; Aro & Upadyaya, 2020). Based on the study of Liu et al. (2023), more than half of students experienced academic burnout. Due to the cultural focus on academic performance, students in East Asian countries particularly South Korea face greater levels of stress and pressure in the classroom (Gloria & Ho, 2003; Lee & Lee, 2018). Moreover, Filipino college students from the northern Philippines have a moderate to high risk for burnout especially female students (Ramos et al., 2021). Likewise, academic burnout contributes to a high dropout rate among students in higher education. Uncertain repercussions are known to result from leaving a computer science course before graduating (Takacs et al., 2022), as experienced by the Bachelor of Science in Computer Science at Isabela State University Echague Campus.

On the other side, hobbies are activities that people engage in during their free time for enjoyment, relaxation, or pleasure (Liu & Da, 2020). Hobbies come in a vast variety and differ greatly from individual to person. These can be artistic endeavors like writing, sketching, or painting, athletic ones like dancing, running, or playing sports, or social ones like playing board games or joining a group (Aksoy, 2019). Hobbies can be categorized into creative, physical, enrichment, social, collecting, outdoor, technological, and relaxation activities (Hartono, 2022). Engaging in these hobbies offers numerous benefits, including reducing stress, improving physical health, enhancing social connections, and promoting personal growth. By engaging in enjoyable experiences, one can have a positive impact on one's mental health and well-being (Scanlan & Hazelton, 2019). Hobbies provide people a chance to unplug from the stresses and strains of daily life so they may concentrate on enjoyable activities and feel proud of what they have accomplished (Thompson & Wilkie, 2021; Sonnentag, 2018). These are frequently viewed as a means to unwind, enhance physical and mental health, and promote a sense of personal development and fulfillment (Abouammoh, 2020). Hobbies can also provide opportunities for social interaction and community involvement, as people generally pursue hobbies with others who share similar interests (Torres, 2022). Social advantages can also come from group activities like team sports or shared interests. Engaging in these activities can improve one's interpersonal interactions, communication abilities, and sense of connection (Pluhar et al., 2019). It is crucial to remember that hobbies can change and be customized to fit different personalities and interests. They may be artistic, athletic, intellectual, or some other form of self-expression. These can be an avenue for self-discovery, personal development, and enjoyment whether they are done alone or in a group (Chan et al., 2021).

Research has shown that engaging in hobbies can promote a state of "flow," which is a mental state of deep focus and absorption in an activity. This state of flow can help reduce stress and anxiety, as well as provide a sense of satisfaction and accomplishment (Koehler et al., 2021). Overall, hobbies can serve as a reset button for our brains, providing a much-needed break from stress and promoting relaxation and rejuvenation (Hyatt, 2019; Lyons, 2019). Research has shown that hobbies can have a positive impact on mental health and well-being, promoting relaxation, reducing stress and anxiety, and increasing satisfaction and enjoyment in life (Gogo et al., 2019). However, the potential role of hobbies in reducing academic burnout remains largely unexplored (Cabal, 2021; Yang, 2021).

This research aimed to investigate how hobbies can help university students feel less academically burned out. The research aimed to figure out how hobbies can prevent students from becoming academically burned out. To solve their issue, the researchers needed evidence about how beneficial recreational activities are from the learners' own experiences while engaging in those activities. Specifically, the study aimed to gather the BSCS respondents' demographic data; identify the two hobbies that BSCS members enjoy most and are most engaged in; determine whether hobbies benefit students who are trying to avoid, manage, and recover from academic burnout, or whether hobbies have no such effect; if hobbies are found to be helpful in experiencing or preventing academic burnout, which hobbies would be the best course of action for students when coping with burnout-related issues, and for how long should hobbies be practiced each week?; and determine whether hobbies have a favorable effect on the three dimensions of well-being.

The results of this study would fill the gap about the advantages of hobbies as a means of preventing, managing, and eliminating burnout among BSCS students. This study may help create interventions that help students who are experiencing academic burnout, especially those that promote participation in hobbies as a way to improve mental health and wellness. The study may also provide important information for the implementation of appropriate interventions by exposing the potential moderating effects of demographic and academic factors on the association between hobbies and academic burnout.

Figure 1. *Theoretical Framework*

The theoretical framework, which charts the path from stress to academic burnout, hobby involvement, and recovery, is a good fit for the objectives of the study. Investigating how hobbies help BSCS students avoid burnout and maintain their well-being offers a structured way of comprehending the relationship between stresses, coping techniques, and recovery measures. This approach informs possible remedies to

improve student well-being and enables a thorough investigation of the efficacy of hobbies in addressing symptoms of burnout. Thus, it strongly aligns with the goals and research aims of the study and allows for a detailed analysis of the links between stress, burnout, hobbies, and recovery.

The physical, mental, emotional stress, and sleep deprivation at this stage represent the various stressors that students may encounter in their academic lives. These stressors can include heavy workloads, deadlines, academic pressure, competition, personal issues, and inadequate sleep. The accumulation of stress from these sources can lead to physical, mental, and emotional exhaustion, as well as sleep disturbances.

The next stage of the theoretical framework is the academic burnout which is the result of prolonged exposure to high levels of stress related to academic activities. It is characterized by emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and a diminished sense of personal accomplishment. Students experiencing academic burnout may feel overwhelmed, disengaged, and apathetic towards their studies.

The third stage is hobbies which represent a potential coping mechanism or intervention to mitigate the effects of academic burnout. Engaging in hobbies provides students with opportunities for relaxation, enjoyment, and personal fulfillment outside of academic pursuits. Hobbies can serve as a form of self-care, allowing students to recharge, reduce stress, and maintain a healthy work-life balance.

The last stage is the recovery which involves the process of recovery from academic burnout through engagement in hobbies. By participating in enjoyable and meaningful activities, students can replenish their energy, restore their motivation, and rebuild their resilience. Hobbies facilitate psychological detachment from academic stressors, promote positive emotions, and enhance overall well-being. Ultimately, the recovery stage aims to help students regain their academic focus, productivity, and sense of fulfillment.

By incorporating hobbies into their lives, students can potentially break the cycle of academic burnout and improve their academic performance, mental health, and overall quality of life.

Methods

This part served as the researchers' foundation for understanding how to evaluate the various hobbies that students engage in if hobbies are beneficial to students, and which hobby is the best for minimizing academic burnout. Also, the research design, evaluation method, locale, and population of the study, sampling method, and ethical considerations were discussed in this section.

Research Design

To achieve the aims of the study, the researcher used the descriptive-normative survey method. According to Levitt, to describe the existence of a phenomenon or phenomena, the descriptive survey method is used (Levitt, 2021). The descriptive normative survey approach was used for this study because it is appropriate for characterizing the presence of a phenomenon, in this case, the contribution of hobbies to BSCS students' minimization of academic burnout. With this approach, information on students' demographic characteristics, experiences with academic burnout, and involvement in extracurricular activities may be systematically gathered and analyzed. The methodical way to collect data on the frequency of burnout symptoms, the kinds of hobbies students participate in, and their opinions about these pursuits were all aligned

with the objectives of the study. Moreover, the research design makes it easier to investigate possible links between hobbies and burnout, which advances knowledge of the ways in which extracurricular activities could affect students' well-being.

Evaluation Method

Results of the study's objective were obtained through the questionnaire. The questionnaire that was utilized was adapted from an Arangel (2021). Part II was designed to help respondents recognize their respective academic burnouts. Following that, participants were surveyed for any burnout symptoms they may have experienced.

The questionnaire utilized in this study was adapted from a previously validated instrument that demonstrated satisfactory reliability in a prior study conducted by Arangel (2021). The reliability of the questionnaire in the current study was confirmed through rigorous assessments conducted in the original study, which included expert review and internal consistency reliability analysis. Given the established reliability of the questionnaire in the previous study, it was deemed appropriate for use in the current study context. The following scale and interpretation were used to better understand the quantitative data in Part II.

Table 1. Interpretation Scale Used in the Research Frequency or Likelihood of an Event

Response Mean	Verbal Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Never
3.40-4.19	Almost Never
2.60-3.39	Occasionally/Sometimes
1.80-2.59	Almost Every Time
1.00-1.79	Every Time

Part III of the survey has questions that helped the researchers understand the kind of hobbies the students were engaging in such as enrichment, sports, creative, social, collecting, and outdoor hobbies. Subsequently, follow-up questions were given, asking the respondents to identify their top two (2) hobbies and the number of hours they allocate to their hobbies in a week.

Part IV then also used Likert Scales to assess the attitudes and views of the respondent about their experiences with academic burnout, hobbies, and both. The previously cited scale and interpretation table was also used to better understand the quantitative data in Part IV.

The types of hobbies that were included were enrichment, sports, creative, social, collecting, and outdoor hobbies. Data tabulation occurred once the data was obtained. The contents of the table included the sex, age, and year level of the respondents, and the table also included the aforementioned types of hobbies. The researchers analyzed the data through the use of frequency distribution. The researchers determined the effectiveness of hobbies by the use of the Likert scale, as well as to know how frequently the respondents experience academic burnout based on the symptoms that they have experienced. The whole survey contains forty-one (41) questions and accomplishing the form typically lasts for almost five (5) minutes only.

The Locale and Respondents of the Study

The researchers' respondents were the BSCS students of the College of Computing Studies, Information and Communication Technology, Isabela State University, San Fabian, Echague, Isabela.

Sampling Method

Purposive or non-probability sampling was the most appropriate technique used for the study, given that the researchers had already determined precisely the respondents of the study. Purposive sampling is the process of choosing participants who are thought to be representatives of the target community based on predetermined criteria or traits (Thomas, 2022). Those who were enrolled in a course that is only open to BSCS students were taken into consideration.

Ethical Considerations

The goal of the study was to determine how to minimize academic burnout through hobbies and identify both the advantages and learner choices. To protect the participants' identities and privacy, only the researchers had access to the names and responses of those who chose to include their identities in the demographic section of the survey. This was done so that they could complete the survey anonymously. Also, none of the respondents were forced into taking part in the research. Participants had the option to not respond to the survey if they felt uncomfortable with the study.

Results and Discussion

The findings of the researchers' survey of BSCS students are presented in this section. This section also included information on the indications of academic burnout, preferred hobbies, and the connection between hobbies and academic burnout.

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

In a sample of 125 students, the frequency and percentage distribution of pupils at various year levels is shown in the following table. Thirty third-year students (24%), 50 first-year students (40%), 22 second-year students (17.6%), and 23 fourth-year students (18.4%) were all represented in the sample.

Table 2. Demographic Profile According to Year Level

Year Levels	Frequency	Percent
1 st Year	50	40
2 nd Year	22	17.6
3 rd Year	30	24
4 th Year	23	18.4
Total	125	100

The frequency and percentage distribution of sex among a sample of 125 respondents are shown in the following table. There were 48 women (38.4%) and 77 men (61.6%).

Table 3. Demographic Profile According to Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percent
Male	77	61.6
Female	48	38.4
Total	125	100

Learners' Academic Burnout Symptoms

Table 4 provides the results of a survey on the frequency of certain experiences related to school tasks and activities. The weighted mean and verbal interpretation are given for each question.

Table 4. Academic Burnout Determinator Likert Scale

Question	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Have you experienced exhaustion in doing schoolwork?	3.46	Almost Every Time
Have you experienced a lack of interest in school tasks and activities?	2.99	Occasionally/Sometimes
Have you experienced missing or failing to attend a class?	2.51	Almost Never
Have you experienced over workload with a lack of sufficient rest?	3.70	Almost Every Time
Have you experienced frequent exhaustion?	3.42	Almost Every Time
Have you experienced frequent body aches?	3.47	Almost Every Time
Have you experienced feelings of negativity, loneliness, helplessness?	3.47	Almost Every Time
Have you experienced exhaustion in doing schoolwork?	3.46	Almost Every Time
Have you experienced a lack of interest in school tasks and activities?	2.99	Occasionally/Sometimes
Have you experienced missing or failing to attend a class?	2.51	Almost Never

The results show that students frequently experienced exhaustion in doing school work, with a weighted mean of 3.46, which is interpreted as "almost every time." They also frequently experienced overworkload with lack of sufficient rest, frequent exhaustion, frequent body aches, and feelings of negativity, loneliness, and helplessness, all with weighted means above 3.4 and verbal interpretations of "almost every time."

On the other hand, students reported occasional or sometimes lack of interest in school tasks and activities, with a weighted mean of 2.99. They rarely missed or failed to attend a class, with a weighted mean of 2.51, which is interpreted as "almost never."

Types of Hobbies and Duration

The following table shows the frequency and percentage distribution of hobbies among a sample of 125 respondents. The sample includes 15 individuals who selected enrichment hobbies (12%), 19 who selected sports hobbies (15.2%), 21 who selected creative hobbies (16.8%), 30 who selected social activities (24%), 7 who selected collecting hobbies (5.6%), and 33 who selected outdoor hobbies (26.4%).

Table 5. Hobbies Selection

Hobbies Selection	Frequency	Percentage
Enrichment Hobbies	15	12
Sport Hobbies	19	15.2
Creative Hobbies	21	16.8
Social Activities	30	24
Collecting	7	5.6
Outdoor Hobbies	33	26.4
Total	125	100

The data suggests that outdoor hobbies are the most common type among the sample, showing the highest frequency. There is a direct correlation between the outdoor built environment and students' physical and mental health, which can lead to reduced stress, increased academic achievement, and motivation to persist through subsequent semesters until graduation. (Dilliard, 2022). Other popular hobbies are social activity, and creative hobbies. The least common type of hobby is collecting hobbies.

Table 6. The Most Favored Hobby

Hobbies Selection	Frequency	Percentage
Enrichment Hobbies	13	10.4
Sport Hobbies	47	37.6
Creative Hobbies	23	18.4
Social Activities	17	13.6
Collecting	3	2.4
Outdoor Hobbies	22	17.6
Total	125	100

The table shows the frequency and percentage distribution of hobbies among a sample of 125 respondents. The sample includes 13 individuals who selected enrichment hobbies (10.4%), 47 who selected sports hobbies (37.6%), 23 who selected creative hobbies (18.4%), 17 who selected social activities (13.6%), 3 who selected collecting hobbies (2.4%), and 22 who selected outdoor hobbies (17.6%). The data suggests that the most common type of hobby among the sample is sports hobbies. Sports may help reduce depression and poor sleep quality in college students. However, physical activity alone may not help improve anxiety and perceived stress (Johnston et al., 2021). Creative hobbies and outdoor activities were also popular choices. The least common types of hobbies among the sample were collecting hobbies and enrichment hobbies.

Table 7. The Second Most Favored Hobby

Hobbies Selection	Frequency	Percentage
Enrichment Hobbies	29	23.2
Sport Hobbies	66	52.8
Creative Hobbies	48	38.4
Social Activities	62	49.6
Collecting	16	12.8
Outdoor Hobbies	63	50.4

Table 7 shows the frequency of the second most favored hobby of the BSCS students. Sports, outdoor, and social activities are the BSCS students' most favored hobbies, as evident in the highest frequency count. The least among the second most favored hobbies of the respondents is collecting, which got the lowest frequency count.

Table 8. Duration of Recreational Activities

Hours per Week	Frequency	Percentage
1-10	71	56.8
11-20	20	16
21-30	15	12
31-40	5	4
41-50	10	8
51-60	0	0
61-70	0	0
71-80	1	.8
81-90	0	0
91-100	3	2.4

The table shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the duration of recreational activities in hours per week among a sample of respondents. The sample includes 71 individuals who spend 1-10 hours per week on recreational activities, representing 56.8% of the sample; 20 respondents (16%) spend 11-20 hours per week on recreational activities; while 15 respondents (12%) spend 21-30 hours per week. Only 1 respondent (0.8%) spends 71-80 hours per week, while 3 respondents (2.4%) spend 91-100 hours per week on recreational activities. The remaining categories of 31-40 hours per week and 41-50 hours per week were selected by 5 and 10 respondents, respectively.

The data suggests that the majority of the sample spends between 1-10 hours per week on recreational activities, while a smaller proportion spends more time on such activities. The percentage of respondents who spend more than 30 hours per week on recreational activities is relatively small, at 16.8% of the sample.

Views on Hobbies and Academic Burnout

The table shows that the respondents agreed that hobbies help them avoid academic burnout and deal with it when it does occur, as indicated by mean scores ranging from 3.07 to 3.23. They also agreed that hobbies have a positive impact on their physical, mental, and emotional health, with mean scores ranging from 3.26 to 3.30.

Additionally, the respondents agreed that hobbies help them recover from academic burnout, become productive again, and improve academically overall, with mean scores ranging from 3.14 to 3.21. Overall, these results suggest that incorporating hobbies into one's academic and personal life may have benefits for both mental and physical well-being, as well as academic success.

Table 9. Perspectives on Hobbies and Academic Burnout

Question	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Hobbies help me avoid Academic burnout.	3.16	Agree
Hobbies help me avoid Academic burnout, even if I lack enough rest.	2.99	Agree
Hobbies help boost my physical health	3.30	Agree
Hobbies help boost my mental health.	3.27	Agree
Hobbies help boost my emotional health.	3.26	Agree
Hobbies help me deal with academic burnout.	3.23	Agree
Hobbies help me recover from academic burnout, even if I lack enough rest	3.07	Agree
Hobbies help me recover faster from academic burnout	3.15	Agree
Hobbies help me to be productive again when I experience	3.14	Agree
Overall, hobbies help me to be better academically.	3.21	Agree

Table 10. Perspectives on Hobbies and Academic Burnouts

Question	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
When I experience academic burnouts, hobbies help me to deal with it.	3.11	Agree
When I try to recuperate from academic burnouts, hobbies play a vital role on my recovery	3.13	Agree
When I lack sleep, hobbies help me recuperate from academic burnouts.	2.94	Agree
When I have experienced academic burnouts, hobbies help me to do well on my studies again	3.06	Agree
When I try to prevent academic burnouts, hobbies play a vital role on the prevention of academic burnouts.	3.1	Agree
When I try to prevent academic burnouts, especially if I lack enough rest, hobbies play an important role on the prevention of it	3.05	Agree
When I practice my hobbies, it helps with my emotional well-being	3.16	Agree

When I practice my hobbies, it helps with my mental well-being	3.15	Agree
When I practice my hobbies, it helps with my physical well-being	3.15	Agree
All in all, when I practice my hobbies, these help me to do well in school matters.	3.13	Agree

Table 10 presents the results of a survey that investigates the relationship between hobbies and academic burnout among students. The weighted mean and verbal interpretation are given for each question. The results suggest that engaging in hobbies can help students deal with academic burnout. Specifically, all the questions related to the benefits of hobbies in dealing with academic burnout received a weighted mean above 3, which is interpreted as "Agree." This indicates that the majority of the respondents agreed that hobbies are useful in dealing with academic burnout, recovering from it, doing well in studies again, and preventing it (Keyserlingk, 2022).

Additionally, practicing hobbies was also found to be beneficial for emotional, mental, and physical well-being, with weighted means ranging from 3.15 to 3.16, indicating that respondents agreed that hobbies can help in promoting overall well-being. Finally, the study shows that practicing hobbies can help students perform well in school matters (Ramadan, 2016) with a weighted mean of 3.13 and an interpretation of "Agree." Overall, the study's results suggest that engaging in hobbies can have positive effects on academic burnout, well-being, and academic performance.

Conclusion and Future Works

The aim of this research was to identify the different types of hobbies that Bachelor of Science in Computer Science students engaged in. Enrichment and social hobbies emerged as the two categories that respondents found to be most interesting. Hobbies are beneficial for dealing with, preventing, and recovering from academic burnout.

When a learner is experiencing any of the three situations related to academic burnout, outdoor hobbies are recommended as the best type of hobby, particularly for those who do not have a preferred hobby. However, all types of hobbies can be effective for learners who have a preferred hobby. In addition to helping learners cope with academic burnout, engaging in hobbies regularly can also lead to positive developments in the three dimensions of health: physical, mental, and emotional.

Based on the study's findings, hobbies are strongly recommended as a means of preventing, managing, and recovering from academic burnout. It is also advised for students to pick a hobby and keep up with it, especially after a rough day or week. The quantity of homework and other schoolwork should be limited so that students have time for self-care. Hobbies can help students avoid academic burnout, manage it, and recover from it. These strategies should also include a healthy diet, adequate rest, and frequent exercise. This study fills a gap in the existing literature regarding the efficiency of hobbies in preventing academic burnout as it found that students are successful in doing so. The theoretical framework of the study supports the notion that hobbies can mitigate academic burnout and facilitate its recovery. According to the researchers, students who live unhealthy lifestyles can potentially benefit from this study.

Despite several limitations, such as sample size constraints and other biases, the results emphasize how crucial it is for students to include hobbies in their lives to

improve their well-being and academic performance. This suggests that to reduce stress and prevent burnout, educational institutions should incorporate hobby-related activities into their curricula. To overcome study limitations and get a deeper understanding of the temporal dynamics of the association between hobbies and burnout, future research should make use of bigger samples and longitudinal methods. Examining certain hobby kinds and individual variations may provide insightful information for customized intervention strategies, which would eventually enhance student support and academic achievement.

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